

Possible Anti-Protozoal Compounds

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4-Chloroquinolines were condensed with imidazole and its derivatives to obtain 4-imidazolyquinolines having no significant anti-protozoal activity.

8-HYDROXYQUINOLINES have variable anti-amebic and trichomonacidal activity⁽¹⁾. These effects may be either due to chelation with ferrous iron necessary for the growth of ameba⁽²⁾ or for killing amebas by inhibiting the supporting micro-organisms or by direct action⁽³⁾. Moreover, 4-substituted 7-chloroquinolines (chloroquine) have anti-amebic activity⁽⁴⁾. Furthermore metronidazole is a direct acting antiamebic agent and it also possesses high anti-trichomonal activity⁽⁵⁾. Imidazole dicarboxamide was found to possess interesting anti-coccidial activity⁽⁶⁾. Many 1-substituted 4 or 5 imidazole derivatives have activity against *T. vaginalis* and *T. foetus*⁽⁷⁾. Considering these facts various 4-substituted imidazolyl 7-chloro-quinoline (I) and also 4-substituted-imidazolyl-8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (II) have been synthesised expecting enhanced anti-protozoal effect.

4, 7-Dichloroquinoline⁽⁸⁾, 2-methyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline,⁽⁹⁾ and 2-methyl-3-n-propyl 4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline⁽¹⁰⁾ have been condensed with imidazole derivatives to form compounds of the types (I) and (II).

Pharmacology: None of the compounds described in this paper were found to be significantly active *in vitro* against *T. vaginalis* and *T. foetus* at a concentration of 12.5 mcg/ml.

Experimental

The above types of compounds were synthesised in three following methods:

Method (a): Equimolecular proportion of 4-chloroquinoline derivative (0.005 mole) and imidazole or its derivative⁽¹¹⁾ (0.005 mole) were refluxed with a

minimum amount of phenol (4ml) in an oil bath for 24 hrs at about 200°. It was then acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether to remove phenol. Aqueous-HCl was separated out and was basified with NH₃ (liquor) when a solid separated out. The solid was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried and it was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

Method (b): A mixture of 4-chloroquinoline derivative (0.005 mole), imidazole or its derivative⁽¹¹⁾ (0.005 mole), xylene (20 ml) and a few drops of pyridine was refluxed in an oil bath for 24 hrs at about 200°. The contents were acidified with dil. HCl and was extracted with ether to remove xylene. The aqueous-HCl layer was basified with NH₃ (liquor) when a solid separated out. It was collected by filtration, washed with water and was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

Method (c): Equimolecular proportion of 4-chloroquinoline derivative (0.005 mole) and imidazole derivative⁽¹¹⁾ (0.005 mole) were mixed thoroughly and the mixture was gently heated in an oil bath at about 200° at reduced pressure for half an hour. The contents

were washed with ether to remove unreacted quinoline derivative and the residual mass acidified with 2(N) HCl. The acid solution was clarified with charcoal and then basified with NH₃ (liquor) when a solid separated out. The solid obtained on filtration was washed with water and was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline: 2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline⁽¹⁰⁾ (6.8 g) was refluxed with 89 ml sulphuric acid (63%) for 7 hrs. The content was basified with NH₃ (liquor) and the solid was collected by filtration. The residue

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TABLE 1—DATA ON 4-(1-IMIDAZOLYL)-7-CHLOROQUINOLINE (I)

Formula	X	Y	M.P. °C	Yield %	Analytical					
					Calcd. %			Found %		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
(i) C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₃ Cl (a)	H	H	266-68 (yellow)	50	62.7	3.48	18.65	62.58	3.45	18.45
(ii) C ₁₂ H ₇ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (a)	H	NO ₂	263-64 (light pink)	55	52.45	2.55	20.4	52.1	2.15	20.15
(iii) C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₃ Cl (a)	Me	H	271-72 (yellow)	65.2	64.06	4.106	17.2	63.9	4.52	17.1
(iv) C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (a)	Me	NO ₂	273-73.5 (yellow)	40	54.07	3.15	19.41	53.67	2.95	19.1

Compounds (i)–(iv) were crystallised from aqueous ethanol.
a=Method used for synthesis.

TABLE 2—DATA ON 2-METHYL 4-(1-IMIDAZOLYL) 8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE(II)

Formula	X	Y	Z	M.P. °C (solvent of crystallisation)	Yield %	Analytical					
						Calcd. %			Found %		
						C	H	N	C	H	N
(v) C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O (a)	H	H	H	109-10 (S ₁)	20	69.33	4.88	18.66	69.1	4.58	18.36
(vi) C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃ (a)	H	NO ₂	H	110-11 (S ₂)	70	57.77	3.7	20.74	57.37	3.52	20.44
(vii) C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₃ O (b)	Me	H	H	115-16 (S ₂)	40	70.2	5.43	17.57	69.9	5.1	17.12
(viii) C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ (b)	Me	NO ₂	H	187-88 (S ₃)	40	59.36	4.22	19.71	58.9	3.88	19.23
(ix) C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O (b)	H	H	n-C ₃ H ₇	155-56 (S ₃)	84	71.9	6.36	15.7	71.45	5.86	75.25
(x) C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ (c)	H	NO ₂	n-C ₃ H ₇	165-66 (S ₁)	63	61.53	5.12	17.94	61.13	4.92	17.48
(xi) C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ O (c)	Me	H	n-C ₃ H ₇	152-53 (S ₁)	55	73.3	6.76	14.94	73.1	6.29	14.64
(xii) C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ (c)	Me	NO ₂	n-C ₃ H ₇	195-96 (S ₁)	30	62.57	5.52	17.17	62.43	5.12	16.92

All compounds crystallised in yellow needles.
(a), (b) and (c)=Methods used for synthesis.
S₁ = Aqueous ethanol ; S₂ = Aqueous acetone ;
S₃ = Benzene-Pet. ether mixture (1:1).

redissolved in dil. HCl (1 : 1), and was treated with NH₃ (liquor), separated solid was filtered and washed well with water. The solid was dried in air and was crystallised from dilute alcohol. Yield was 5.7 g (89% yield), m.p. 50-51°.

Found : C, 66.14 ; H, 5.63 ; N, 5.52.

Calculated for C₁₃H₁₄ONCl : C, 66.24, H, 5.9 ; N, 5.9%.

Data of the synthesized compounds are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

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